

Original Report

In-Hospital Cardiac Complications and Outcomes in Patients with Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia

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Abstract

Background:

Patients with chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) are often older and comorbid, raising concerns about elevated cardiovascular (CV) risk. Whether CLL itself independently contributes to cardiac complications remains uncertain.

Objectives:

To evaluate the prevalence and outcomes of major cardiac complications among hospitalized CLL patients, compared with matched non-CLL hospitalizations, in a large, nationally representative dataset.

Methods:

We performed a retrospective cohort study using the 2020–2022 National Inpatient Sample. Adult hospitalizations with CLL were identified using ICD-10 codes. Outcomes included arrhythmia, heart failure, acute myocardial infarction (MI), and cardiac arrest. Secondary outcomes were in-hospital mortality, length of stay (LOS), and total hospital charges. Propensity score weighting with inverse probability of treatment weighting was applied to

balance demographic, comorbidity, and hospital-level covariates between CLL and non-CLL cohorts.

Results:

We identified 92,538 weighted CLL hospitalizations (mean age 75.4 years; 38% female). Cardiac complication prevalence was 35.1% for arrhythmia, 28.3% for heart failure, 5.5% for MI, and 1.3% for cardiac arrest. After weighting, odds of cardiac complications were not significantly different between CLL and non-CLL hospitalizations (all ORs \approx 1.0). Within CLL hospitalizations, arrhythmia (OR 1.32; 95% CI 1.21–1.44) and MI (OR 1.95; 95% CI 1.69–2.24) were associated with increased in-hospital mortality, while all major complications contributed to longer LOS (5–22%) and higher costs (9–66%).

Conclusions:

Hospitalized CLL patients experience a high absolute burden of cardiac complications, but no excess relative risk compared with non-CLL hospitalizations after adjustment. Cardiac events, particularly arrhythmia and MI, substantially worsen outcomes, underscoring the need for proactive cardiovascular management.

Keywords: arrhythmia, acute coronary syndrome, heart failure, risk factor, tyrosine kinase inhibitor

Introduction:

Chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) is the most common adult leukemia in Western countries, and it represents roughly one-quarter of all cases of leukemia in the United States. It is typically diagnosed at an older age, with a median age at presentation exceeding 70 years^{1,2}. Bruton tyrosine kinase (BTK) inhibitors have demonstrated safety and efficacy and are now a preferred first-line option for many patients³.

These therapeutic advances, however, have introduced new cardiovascular (CV) concerns. Early-generation BTK inhibitors, particularly ibrutinib, are associated with a

significantly increased risk of atrial fibrillation (AF), hypertension, and potentially fatal arrhythmias^{4–6}. Data suggests that second-generation agents such as acalabrutinib and zanubrutinib reduce, but do not eliminate these risks^{7,8}. Other CLL therapies, including venetoclax, may also contribute to CV toxicity through off-target effects or by exacerbating vulnerability in older, comorbid populations⁹.

Beyond treatment-related toxicity, there is growing interest in whether CLL itself predisposes patients to cardiovascular disease. Mechanistic studies suggest that chronic inflammation, immune dysregulation, and

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hematologic alterations in CLL may result in a pro-thrombotic or pro-arrhythmic environment. In a previous biomarker study of 139 untreated CLL patients, concentrations of established cardiovascular risk markers, including GDF15 and myostatin, were significantly higher than in healthy controls¹⁰. Reviews of CLL biology further support this link, describing elevated inflammatory cytokine activity and activation of signaling pathways such as NF- κ B and STAT3 that could contribute to cardiovascular injury¹¹.

Registry analyses have reported comparable findings. A Swedish nationwide registry study of over 4,200 CLL patients and matched comparators found similar baseline cardiovascular disease prevalence but a significantly higher incidence of new cardiovascular events during follow-up in the CLL cohort (HR 1.69, 95% CI 1.61–1.77)¹². This excess risk was observed irrespective of prior cardiovascular history or whether patients ultimately required therapy, suggesting a possible disease-related contribution. Nonetheless, because registry data do not capture detailed treatment exposures, residual confounding cannot be excluded.

Overall, while biomarker and registry-based studies raise the possibility that CLL itself increases cardiovascular risk, the evidence remains limited and inconclusive. This uncertainty highlights the importance of large, rigorously controlled studies, especially those comparing treatment-naïve CLL patients with matched controls, to clarify whether CLL independently contributes to cardiovascular complications.

In this context, we conducted a propensity-score weighted, nationwide analysis using the U.S. National Inpatient Sample (NIS). We compared the prevalence of major cardiac complications including arrhythmia, heart failure, acute myocardial infarction (MI), and cardiac arrest between hospitalized patients with and without CLL. We further evaluated the impact of these complications on in-hospital mortality, length of stay (LOS), and total hospital charges. This approach provides contemporary, nationally representative estimates and helps clarify whether CLL itself is a risk factor for cardiac events in the inpatient setting.

Methods

Data Source and Study Design

We performed a retrospective cohort study using the 2020–2022 NIS, the largest publicly available all-payer inpatient database in the United States. The NIS, maintained by the Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project (HCUP) of the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ). This dataset contains deidentified discharge records from approximately 7 million hospital stays annually, representing over 35 million discharges when weighted.

Study Population

All adult hospitalizations, defined as patients aged 18 years or older, were screened for CLL using International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) codes. Hospitalizations without CLL comprised the comparison group. We excluded records missing age, sex, in-hospital mortality, or primary outcome variables.

Variables and Outcomes

The primary outcomes were in-hospital arrhythmia, heart failure, acute myocardial infarction (MI), and cardiac arrest, identified using ICD-10-CM codes (see Supplemental Table 1). Secondary outcomes included in-hospital mortality, length of stay (LOS), and total hospital charges (TOTCHG). LOS was measured in days, and TOTCHG (as defined by HCUP) was inflation-adjusted to 2020 U.S. dollars.

Patient-level covariates included demographics (age, sex, race/ethnicity, primary payer, and ZIP code-based median household income quartile), comorbidities (assessed using the Elixhauser Comorbidity Index), and hospital-level characteristics (teaching status, bed size, location, and U.S. Census region).

Propensity Score Weighting

To minimize confounding, inverse probability of treatment weighting (IPTW) was applied using propensity scores estimated from a logistic regression model including all patient- and hospital-level covariates. Stabilized weights were used to preserve sample size and improve efficiency. Covariate balance between CLL and non-CLL groups was evaluated using standardized mean differences, with values below 0.10 indicating adequate balance.

Statistical Analysis

Weighted logistic regression models were used to estimate odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for the association between CLL and each cardiac complication. Within the CLL subgroup, additional models evaluated the association between each complication and in-hospital mortality.

LOS and TOTCHG were analyzed using generalized linear models with a gamma distribution and log link to account for skewed distributions. Results were expressed as percentage changes relative to the non-CLL group, with 95% CIs.

All analyses incorporated both NIS sampling weights and IPTW weights to generate nationally representative, adjusted estimates. Statistical significance was defined as a two-tailed p-value <0.05. Analyses were performed using Stata/SE 17.0 (StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX).

Ethics Statement

The NIS contains de-identified, publicly available data;

therefore, this study was exempt from institutional review board approval and informed consent.

Results

Baseline characteristics

A total of 92,538 weighted hospitalizations with a diagnosis of CLL were identified from the 2020–2022 NIS. The mean patient age was 75.41 years (95% CI 75.28–75.54), and 38.0% (95% CI 37.57–38.51) were female. The majority of patients were White (85.0%), followed by Black (8.1%), Hispanic (3.7%), Asian/Pacific Islander (1.0%), Native American (0.2%), and Other races (2.1%). Most patients were covered by Medicare (79.5%), and the mean length of stay (LOS) was 6.14 days (95% CI 6.08–6.20). The mean total hospital charges were \$75,080 (95% CI \$73,981–\$76,178).

Prevalence of cardiac complications

The prevalence of arrhythmia was 35.1%, heart failure 28.3%, acute myocardial infarction (MI) 5.5%, and cardiac arrest 1.3% among CLL hospitalizations.

Comparison of CLL vs non-CLL hospitalizations

After weighting, the odds of arrhythmia, heart failure, acute MI, and cardiac arrest were not significantly different between CLL and non-CLL hospitalizations (all ORs ≈ 1.0). Odds ratios (OR) were 1.00 (95% CI 0.97–1.03; p=0.956) for arrhythmia, 1.00 (95% CI 0.97–1.03; p=1.000) for heart failure, 1.00 (95% CI 0.94–1.06; p=0.977) for acute MI, and 1.03 (95% CI 0.91–1.16; p=0.671) for cardiac arrest.

Associations with in-hospital mortality

In the CLL cohort, arrhythmia (OR 1.320, 95% CI 1.211–1.438; p<0.001) and acute MI (OR 1.947, 95% CI 1.693–2.240; p<0.001) were associated with higher odds of in-hospital mortality, whereas heart failure did not show a statistically significant association (OR 1.067, 95% CI 0.972–1.171; p=0.172). Presence of cancer other than CLL was associated with a markedly elevated risk of in-hospital mortality.

Cumulative cardiac risk score

We created a cumulative cardiac risk score by summing the presence of arrhythmia, heart failure, MI, and cancer other than CLL (range 0–4). Each 1-point increase was associated with 61% higher odds of mortality (OR 1.61, 95% CI 1.54–1.68).

Length of stay and hospitalization costs

Among CLL hospitalizations, cardiac complications were strongly associated with increased resource use. Arrhythmia was associated with an approximately 11% longer hospital stay and 15% higher costs, while heart failure was associated with an 11% longer stay and 9% higher costs. Myocardial infarction was linked to a 6% longer stay and 39% higher costs, and the presence of another malignancy contributed to a 22% longer stay and 66% higher costs (all p<0.001). (Table 1)..

Table 1. Associations of cardiac complications with in-hospital outcomes among CLL hospitalizations

Outcome	Predictor	OR / IRR / Cost Ratio (95% CI)	% Change (approx.)	p-value
In-hospital mortality	Arrhythmia	1.320 (1.211–1.438)	+32% odds	<0.001
	Heart failure	1.067 (0.972–1.171)	+7% (NS)	0.172
	Myocardial infarction	1.947 (1.693–2.240)	+95% odds	<0.001
	Cancer (other than CLL)	1.52 (1.418–1.647)	+52% odds	<0.001
Length of stay	Risk score (per point)	1.611 (1.542–1.684)	+61% per point	<0.001
	Arrhythmia	1.108 (1.085–1.131)	10.80%	<0.001
	Heart failure	1.115 (1.091–1.139)	11.50%	<0.001
	Myocardial infarction	1.057 (1.017–1.099)	5.70%	0.005
Hospitalization costs	Cancer (other than CLL)	1.221 (1.118–1.333)	22.10%	<0.001
	Arrhythmia	1.152 (1.128–1.177)	15.20%	<0.001
	Heart failure	1.092 (1.069–1.116)	9.20%	<0.001
	Myocardial infarction	1.390 (1.338–1.444)	39.00%	<0.001
	Cancer (other than CLL)	1.656 (1.535–1.787)	65.60%	<0.001

Discussion

In this large, nationally representative inpatient analysis, we provide the first propensity-weighted evidence that chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) itself may not confer excess risk of acute cardiac complications during hospitalization, despite biologic plausibility and prior

registry signals. Instead, the burden of cardiac events in CLL appears largely driven by comorbidities and co-existing clinical factors rather than the leukemia per se.

Our results differ from several earlier observational and registry-based studies, which reported higher rates of cardiovascular morbidity in CLL, often attributed to disease-related immune dysregulation, chronic inflammation, or treatment-related cardiotoxicity^{10, 12}. Importantly, those analyses often included treated patients and lacked rigorous adjustment for baseline comorbidity burden. By contrast, our use of propensity score weighting allowed for balanced cardiovascular risk profiles between groups, which may explain why we observed no excess risk in adjusted analyses.

Within the CLL cohort, however, the presence of cardiac complications was strongly associated with adverse hospital outcomes. Arrhythmia and acute myocardial infarction (MI) significantly increased in-hospital mortality risk, with acute MI nearly doubling the odds of death—highlighting ischemic events as the most lethal cardiac complication in this setting. All major cardiac complications were also linked to longer hospital stays and higher costs, and mortality rose stepwise with each point increase in cumulative cardiac risk scores. These findings underscore that although CLL itself may not independently elevate risk, the clinical and economic burden of cardiac complications in this population remains substantial.

From a clinical perspective, these data argue for embedding cardiovascular risk stratification into inpatient care pathways for CLL. Proactive monitoring for arrhythmias, optimization of heart failure therapy, and aggressive secondary prevention for ischemic heart disease may help mitigate adverse outcomes. Such an approach aligns with broader cardio-oncology efforts to integrate cancer and cardiovascular care.

Our study also provides a contemporary benchmark for cardiac complication prevalence in hospitalized CLL patients in the post-targeted therapy era. As CLL management continues to evolve with the widespread use of Bruton's tyrosine kinase (BTK) inhibitors and other targeted agents, longitudinal surveillance will be essential to detect shifts in cardiovascular risk patterns over time.

This study has limitations. Use of the National Inpatient Sample (NIS) introduces potential coding errors and misclassification, and the database lacks granular information such as CLL stage, treatment history, or outpatient medication use, limiting assessment of therapy-specific cardiotoxicity. Although propensity score weighting balanced observed covariates between CLL and non-CLL groups, residual confounding from unmeasured variables remains possible.

Furthermore, the NIS does not differentiate between pre-existing and incident complications within a hospitalization, limiting assessment of temporality. Because only inpatient events are captured, our results reflect acute, hospitalization-associated complications and may underestimate the overall cardiovascular burden. Finally, as this is an observational study, associations should not be interpreted as causal.

Taken together, these findings suggest that while hospitalized patients with CLL experience a high absolute burden of cardiac complications, their relative risk compared with non-CLL peers is not independently elevated. Future studies linking detailed treatment exposures, outpatient follow-up, and longitudinal cardiovascular outcomes are essential to disentangle the contributions of CLL biology versus therapy to cardiovascular risk.

Conclusion

In this large, nationally representative inpatient study, we found that hospitalized patients with CLL experience a substantial burden of cardiac complications, yet their relative risk compared with non-CLL peers was not independently elevated after rigorous adjustment for comorbidities. Within the CLL cohort, arrhythmia and acute MI were particularly impactful, contributing to markedly higher in-hospital mortality, prolonged length of stay, and increased costs. These findings highlight the importance of proactive cardiovascular risk stratification and management during hospitalization, even in the absence of a CLL-specific excess risk. As treatment paradigms continue to evolve, future longitudinal studies integrating treatment exposures and outpatient outcomes will be essential to clarify the interplay between CLL biology, therapy, and cardiovascular risk.

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